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SMARTPHONE-ASSISTED STUDENT FEEDBACK TO LECTURERS FOR BETTER ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

One way to work on improving engineering education is to collect and use student feedback about lecturers' teaching quality. However, as a lecturer in engineering education, it is not always easy to obtain such feedback. Therefore, the Impact! tool was developed. Students fill in a short questionnaire anonymously right at the end of the lecture just delivered. The questions reflect scientifically investigated characteristics of effective lessons. Summaries of students' ratings are provided to lecturers. This way, student perceptions could be an important basis for lecturers' reflections on their teaching and, how their lectures can be improved. Workshop participants will experience using the Impact! tool and we will discuss how student feedback can be used effectively for improving engineering education. Moreover, results of research into the use of the impact tool will be presented and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

A goal of the Quality Agreements of the University of Twente is to improve the quality of (engineering) education. Therefore, normally student perceptions are collected regarding the quality of a whole course that has ended. However, there is much time between receiving the results and the start of next year's course. Moreover, the feedback is often about the *overall* course quality, what causes problems if a course is delivered by more than one lecturer. The digital feedback tool 'Impact!' makes it possible for lecturers to obtain feedback from students right at the end of each lecture, in a few minutes. The feedback gives lecturers insight into the strengths of their lecture, and into areas where improvement is possible. Lecturers thus can work on improving their follow-up lectures immediately. The students of that course can directly benefit

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from that (rather than providing feedback at the end of a course, when it is too late to improve this year's course).

The Impact! tool was initially developed for use in secondary schools. Because of its success, we developed and tested a version of the tool for university lectures. Lecturers used the tool during a pilot in their lectures, to obtain student feedback as a basis for improving their teaching. The student feedback they obtained was found to be relevant for improving follow-up lectures, especially for starting lecturers. The tool is being implemented at a larger scale within three faculties of the University of Twente.

2 WHAT ARE SESSION PARTICIPANTS EXPECTED TO LEARN?

In this digital workshop, we will present the content and the features of the Impact tool. Participants will experience using the tool. Furthermore, research findings and recommendations for the implementation of Impact! in engineering education will be discussed with the audience as well as preconditions for improving lectures based on student feedback.

3 WHY IS THE SESSION RELEVANT?

The digital 'Impact!' tool provides lecturers with student feedback about the degree to which their lecture that just ended meets the characteristics of effective lessons. Because the feedback is sent to the teachers right after the lecture, the link between their actual teaching in the lecture and the feedback received can be made better, than in the case of general feedback at the end of a whole course. In the workshop, participants will discuss possible implementations of students feedback by means of the Impact! tool in their own educational practice.

4 HOW ARE SESSION PARTICIPANTS ACTIVATED?

Participants will experience using the tool. They can easily do this with their own smartphone when they are joining the workshop at home. By using the digital brainstorm tool 'Padlet', research findings and recommendations for the implementation of Impact! in engineering education will be discussed with the audience.

5 TAKE HOME MESSAGE FOR SESSION PARTICIPANTS

Student feedback by means of the Impact tool can encourage and support lecturers to improve the quality of their lectures. We know that a sustainable improvement of lecture quality requires more than only obtaining feedback: clear support on what and how to improve, and sometimes also coaching during the improvement process are important for improving lectures.

6 HOW IS THIS WORK SIGNIFICANT FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION?

This workshop shows a practical way how to collect and use student feedback within the context of engineering education in-between lecturers. As such, it will be an interesting workshop for lecturers working in engineering education as they can experience using the Impact! tool and will learn about the relevant preconditions for

using student feedback in such a way it will affect their own lecturing in an effective positive way.